

SOME CONCEPTS ABOUT POLYNOMIALS

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Abstract. In this article, we provide some information about polynomial problems and how to solve them.

Keywords: polynomial, root, triangle.

$$1. P(x) \leftrightarrow D(P) - \text{number} \quad 1) D(\alpha_1 P_1 + \alpha_2 P_2) = \alpha_1 D(P_1) + \alpha_2 D(P_2)$$

$$2) D(P_1 \times P_2) = D(P_1)P_2\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + P_1\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)D(P_2) \quad \alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in R \quad a) D(P) = aP'\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = ?$$

$$P(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$$

$$\text{Method 1. } D(x^2) = D(x \times x) = D(x) \times \frac{1}{2} + D(x) \times \frac{1}{2} = D(x) = a$$

$$D(x^3) = D(x^2 \times x) = D(x^2) \times \frac{1}{2} + D(x) \times \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4}a$$

$$D(x^4) = D(x^3 \times x) = D(x^3) \times \frac{1}{2} + D(x) \times \frac{1}{8} = \frac{a}{2}$$

$$D(x^5) = D(x^4 \times x) = D(x^4) \times \frac{1}{2} + D(x) \times \frac{1}{16} = \frac{5a}{16}$$

$$D(x^n) = \frac{na}{2^{n-1}}$$

$$D(a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0) = a_n D(x^n) + D(a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0) =$$

$$= a_n \times \frac{na}{2^{n-1}} + a_{n-1} \times \frac{(n-1)a}{2^{n-2}} + \dots + a_1 \times a = a \times \left(\frac{a_n n}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{a_{n-1}(n-1)}{2^{n-2}} + \dots + a_1 \right) =$$

$$aP'\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), D(a_0) = 0$$

$$\text{Method 2. } P(x) - P\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)q(x), D\left(P(x) - P\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\right) = D(\rho)$$

$$D\left(\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)q(x)\right) = D\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)q\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = D(x)q\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D(d) = 0 \\ D(x) = c \\ c, d - \forall \text{ number} \end{array} \right. , \quad D(P) = D(x)q\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}} \frac{P(x) - P\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{x - \frac{1}{2}} = q\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = P'\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \quad D(P) =$$

$$D(x)P'\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$$

$$D(P) = CP'\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$$

b) f function is continuous on $[0, 1]$ and for an arbitrary function $D(f) = 0$ and $f \leftrightarrow D(f)$

$$1) D(\alpha_1 f_1 + \alpha_2 f_2) = \alpha_1 D(f_1) + \alpha_2 D(f_2)$$

$$2) D(f_1 \times f_2) = D(f_1) \times f_2\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + D(f_2) \times f_1\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), P(x) \leftrightarrow D(P) - \text{number}$$

$$1) D(\alpha_1 P_1 + \alpha_2 P_2) = \alpha_1 D(P_1) + \alpha_2 D(P_2)$$

$$2) D(P_1 \times P_2) = D(P_1)P_2(x_0) + D(P_2)P_1(x_0)$$

$$x_0 - \text{const}, D(P) = P'(x_0), D(x_0) = 0, D(x) = c$$

$$\text{Method 1. } P(x) - P(x_0) = (x - x_0)q(x), D(P(x) - P(x_0)) = D(P)$$

$$D((x - x_0)q(x)) = D(x - x_0)q(x) = D(x)q(x_0) = cq(x_0)$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{P(x) - P(x_0)}{x - x_0} = P'(x_0) = q(x_0), D(P) = cq(x_0) \Rightarrow D(P) = cP'(x_0)$$

Method 2. $D(x_0) = 0 \quad D(x) = c, P(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$

$$D(x^2) = D(x \times x) = D(x) \times x_0 + D(x) \times x_0 = 2D(x) \times x_0 = 2cx_0$$

$$D(x^3) = D(x^2 \times x) = D(x^2) \times x_0 + D(x) \times x_0^2 = 2cx_0^2 + cx_0^2 = 3cx_0^2$$

$$D(x^4) = D(x^3 \times x) = D(x^3) \times x_0 + D(x) \times x_0^3 = 3cx_0^3 + cx_0^3 = 4cx_0^3$$

$$D(x^5) = D(x^4 \times x) = D(x^4) \times x_0 + D(x) \times x_0^4 = 4cx_0^4 + cx_0^4 = 5cx_0^4$$

$$D(x^n) = ncx_0^{n-1}$$

$$D(a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0) = a_n n c x_0^{n-1} + a_{n-1} (n-1) c x_0^{n-2} + \dots + a_2 c + a_1 = c \times P'(x_0) \Rightarrow D(P) = cP'(x_0)$$

2. $P(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$

$$P(a) \geq 0; P'(a) \geq 0; \dots, P^{(n-1)}(a) \geq 0; P^n(a) > 0$$

$$P^n(a) = n! a_n > 0 \Rightarrow a_n > 0, P^{n-1}(a) = n! a_n + a_{n-1} (n-1)!$$

$$P^{n+1}(x) = 0, P(x_0) = 0, x_0 \leq a?, P(x) \uparrow [a; +\infty) \ni x \forall$$

We expand on Taylor series at $x = a$.

$$P(x) = \frac{P'(a)}{1!} (x - a) + \frac{P''(a)}{2!} (x - a)^2 + \dots + \frac{P^n(a)}{n!} (x - a)^n$$

$$P(x) = b_n (x - a)^n + b_{n-1} (x - a)^{n-1} + \dots + b_1 (x - a) + b_0$$

$$b_n = \frac{P^n(a)}{n!} > 0$$

So, $-a > 0 \Rightarrow P(x) > 0 \cdot x > a \quad P(x) > 0 \Rightarrow P(x)$ the root of the polynomial satisfies the inequality $x < a$.

3. $x^n - P(x) = 0$

Method 1. $P(x) = a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + a_{n-2} x^{n-2} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0; \quad a_i > 0, i = \overline{0, n-1},$
 $x^n - P(x) = 0$

$$Q(x) = x^n - a_{n-1} x^{n-1} - a_{n-2} x^{n-2} \dots - a_1 x + a_0$$

$$Q(0) = -a_0 < 0$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} Q(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} x^n \left(1 - \frac{a_{n-1}}{x} - \frac{a_{n-2}}{x^2} - \dots - \frac{a_1}{x^{n-1}} - \frac{a_0}{x^n} \right) = +\infty \Leftrightarrow \forall M > 0; \exists \delta \in \mathbb{R} \quad x > \delta, x \in [0, +\infty)$$

$$Q(x) > M > 0 \text{ will be } x > \delta \Leftrightarrow (\delta, +\infty)$$

So, $[0, 2\delta]$ in the interval $Q(x)$ is polynomially continuous and $(0) \times Q(2\delta) < 0! \Rightarrow \exists x_0 [0, 2\delta], Q(x_0) \equiv 0$

Now we show that x_0 is unique. Inverse hypothesis: do not be unique. That is $\exists x_1 [0, +\infty)$

$Q(x_0) = Q(x_1) = 0$ so be it.

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= Q(x_0) - Q(x_1) = (x_0^n - x_1^n) - a_{n-1}(x_0^{n-1} - x_1^{n-1}) - \dots - a_1(x_0 - x_1) \\ &= (x_0 - x_1) \left(a_n \sum_{i=1}^n x_0^{n-i} \times x_1^{i-1} - a_{n-1} \sum_{i=2}^n x_0^{n-i} \times x_1^{i-2} - \dots \right. \\ &\quad \left. - a_{n-k+1} \sum_{i=k}^n x_0^{n-i} \times x_1^{i-k} - a_1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$y_0^{n-x} = \sum_{i=k}^n x_0^{n-i} \times x_1^{i-k}$$

$$(x_0 - x_1)(y_0^{n-1} - a_{n-1}y_0^{n-2} - \dots - a_1) = (x_0 - x_1)D(y_0) = 0$$

$$D(y) = y_0^{n-1} - a_{n-1}y_0^{n-2} - \dots - a_1$$

- $$\begin{cases} 1) x_0 = x_1, D(y_0) \neq 0 \\ 2) x_0 = x_1 \text{ va } D(y_0) = 0 \quad ? \\ 3) x_0 = x_1, D(y_0) = 0 \end{cases}$$

If $a_0 = 0$, $Q(x) = x^n - a_{n-1}x^{n-1} - a_{n-2}x^{n-2} \dots - a_1x = x(x^{n-1} - a_{n-1}x^{n-2} - a_{n-2}x^{n-3} \dots - a_2x - a_1)$

$$Q_1(x) = x^{n-1} - a_{n-1}x^{n-2} - a_{n-2}x^{n-3} \dots - a_2x - a_1$$

$$Q_1(0) = -a_1 < 0 \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} Q_1(x) = +\infty \quad \exists x_0 \in (0, 2\delta) \quad Q(x_0) = 0 \quad x \rightarrow \lambda x$$

$\lambda = \max \{\text{positive root}\}$

$$x^n = a_{n-1}x^{n-1} + a_{n-2}x^{n-2} + \dots + a_1x + a_0$$

$$\lambda^n x^n = a_{n-1}\lambda^{n-1}x^{n-1} + a_{n-2}\lambda^{n-2}x^{n-2} + \dots + a_1\lambda x + a_0$$

So x_0 is not a root.

$$x^n = a_{n-1} \frac{x^{n-1}}{\lambda} + a_{n-2} \frac{x^{n-2}}{\lambda^2} + \dots + a_1 \frac{x}{\lambda^{n-1}} + \frac{a_0}{\lambda^n}$$

$x = 1$ root

$$1 = \frac{a^{n-1}}{\lambda} + \frac{a^{n-2}}{\lambda^2} + \dots + \frac{a_1}{\lambda^{n-1}} + \frac{a_0}{\lambda^n}$$

$$1 = b_{n-1} + b_{n-2} + \dots + b_1 + b_0$$

$$0 < x < 1$$

$$x_0^n = a_{n-1} \frac{x_0^{n-1}}{\lambda} + a_{n-2} \frac{x_0^{n-2}}{\lambda^2} + \dots + a_1 \frac{x_0}{\lambda^{n-1}} + \frac{a_0}{\lambda^n}$$

$$1 = \frac{b^{n-1}}{x_0} + \frac{b^{n-2}}{x_0^2} + \dots + \frac{b_1}{x_0^{n-1}} + \frac{b_0}{x_0^n} > b_{n-1} + b_{n-2} + \dots + b_1 + b_0 = 1$$

4. $P(x) = a_0x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + \dots + a_n$

$P(x_{11}) = P(x_{12}) = \dots = P(x_{1n}) = 0$ if so, according to Roll's theorem,

$P'(x_{21}) = P'(x_{22}) = \dots = P'(x_{2,n-1}) = 0$ that is, The roots of $P'(x)$ are real, i.e $P'(x) -$ if we use Roll's theorem for the polynomial,

$P''(x_{31}) = P''(x_{32}) = \dots = P''(x_{3,n-2}) = 0$ that is, The roots of $P''(x)$ are real, i.e. $P''(x)$ if we use Roll's theorem for the polynomial, we will have $P'''(x), \dots, P^{(n-1)}(x), P^{(n-1)}(x_{11}) = 0$

So, $P'(x), P''(x), \dots, P^{(n-1)}(x)$ will have a real root.

5. $P(x) -$ all roots are real $\Rightarrow P(x) = (x - \alpha_1)^{k_1}(x - \alpha_2)^{k_2} \dots (x - \alpha_m)^{k_m}$
 $k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_m = n.$

$P'(x) = (x - \alpha_1)^{k_1-1}(x - \alpha_2)^{k_2-1} \dots (x - \alpha_m)^{k_m-1}Q(x) \Rightarrow P'(x)$ is polynomial only $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m$ and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} c_1 \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \\ c_2 \in (\alpha_2, \alpha_3) \\ c_3 \in (\alpha_3, \alpha_4) \\ \dots \dots \dots \\ c_{m-1} \in (\alpha_{m-1}, \alpha_m) \end{array} \right.$$

$a - P'(x)$ the multiple root of the polynomial, but $c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots, c_{m-1} - P'(x)$ are not multiple roots of the polynomial. So, the root a is equal to one of the $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m$.

But $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m$ $P(x)$ because the polynomial has roots $P(a) = 0$.

$\exists i (i = \overline{1, m}). k_i \geq 3.$

6. $c_0 + \frac{c_1}{2} + \dots + \frac{c_n}{n+1} = 0$ if so, then $P(x) = c_0 + c_1x + \dots + c_nx^n$ has at least 1 real root?

$$Q'(x) = P(x)$$

$$Q(x) = c_0x + \frac{c_1}{2}x^2 + \dots + \frac{c_n}{n+1}x^{n+1}$$

$$Q(0) = 0. Q(1) = c_0 + \frac{c_1}{2} + \dots + \frac{c_n}{n+1} = 0$$

$[0,1]$ The condition of Roll's theorem is valid for $Q(x)$ polynomial.

So, $\exists x_0 \in (0,1), Q(x_0) = P(x_0) = 0. \quad x_0 \in R!$

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